

ISic000537

Fragment of a dedication to Venus Erycina

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object

Statue base

Editor

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Autopsy

Vacanti 2021-08-20

Last Change

2021-09-15 - encoded text, added apparatus, translation, commentary and photograph

Place of origin (ancient)

Eryx

Place of origin (modern)

Erice

Provenance

Eryx, discovered under the ruins of the temple of Venus Erycina at the end of the 18th century according to Hager (1799, 10) . The now lost fragment would have been found in the temple too. It was discovered in 1616 according to

Cordici.

Coordinates

38.035247, 12.592056

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Trapani, Museo Regionale Agostino Pepoli, inventory 5227

Physical Description

A statue base, according to Mommsen 1883 (CIL 10.7257) and Bücheler (CIL 2.7257). A stone slab with fractures on all sides. The surviving piece has an irregular rectangular shape. The fracture on the left side cuts the stone from top to bottom at an angle of about 20 degrees, which then decreases gradually. The fracture on the right side is almost parallel to the one on the left. The base therefore widens from bottom to top on the left side, while on the right side it narrows. The two fractures cut the text of the inscription irregularly to the left and right, while the inscription does not seem to continue at either the bottom or the top. The back of the stone appears roughly worked.

Dimensions

Height 26 cm

Width 33 cm

Depth 12 cm

Layout

The text is arranged over nine lines. The first two lines (praescriptio), larger than the others, are placed across the top. Two columns follow (b and c), the first one consisting of two lines (and a vacat) and the second one of seven. Lines 1-2 of the left column form a separate text from lines 1-2 in the right column. The space between the columns is 2.4 cm.

Execution

Letter Forms

Scriptura actuaria with letters made with the brush edge at an angle of less than 30 degrees to the writing line (rustica). All letters, except the last "a" in column 2, line 8, are rubricated, but most of the colour appears too bright to be ancient (and appears identical to that with which the inventory number on the lower left corner has been applied); it also appears that not all the interpuncts have been rubricated.

Letter heights:

Line a 1: 33 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line a1 to a2: 13 mm

Line a2: 28 mm

Interlineation line a2 to bc1: 10 mm

columns b, c, codicil: 11 mm

Interlineation columns b, c, codicil: 6 mm

Text

Apparatus

Text after CIL 10.7257 (Mommsen 1883) and autopsy of fragment

Mommsen 1875: [Caesianu]s

Cordici P and C: -S

Mommsen 1875: [de sua pecunia Vene]ri

Bücheler (CLE 2.7257) (apparatus): [patris ubi missu dux te, dea, prae]sule

Bücheler (CLE 2.7257): [dum miscet Numidis, prosternitur imp]ius

Bücheler (CLE 2.7257) (apparatus): [prospera pugnavit, cecidit Maurus]ius hostis

Bücheler (CLE 2.7257): [tibi qui sacramque dicavit]

Bücheler (CLE 2.7257): [miles bonus, o dea,]

Gualtherus 1624(1): VDDVXQVE

Gualtherus 1624(1) and 1624(2): LVCTOR

Cordici P and C: IVCTOR

Tardia: LICTOR

Mommsen 1875: hic [claro certamine vi]ctor

Gualtherus 1624(1): QVMPTAE

Cordici C: SUMPTE

Tardia: ORIA PTAE

Mommsen (1874 letter to Hernandez in Muscolino 2013, 464): praetextae
positae [tempore o qualche cosa simile] (sic!)

Gualtherus 1624(2): OCARAT

Cordici P and C: ECHI (inverting line 5 with line 6)

Tardia: OGAD[-]JAT

Mommsen (1875): [r]ogarat

Dessau 1893 (ILS 937): r]o[g]arat

Cordici P and C: ICPIT (inverting line 6 with line 5)

Gualtherus 1624(1): ICPIT

Gualtherus 1624(2): ICVI

Bücheler (CLE 2.7257): rel[i]quit]

Olivieri: DEDER

Tardia: DIVOM

Tardia: MUTA
Gualtherus 1624(1) and 1624(2): MAIC
Cordici P and C: MALO
Muratori; Burmann; Meyer: MAI
Castelli 1769 and 1784: MAIO
Gualtherus 1624(1): GENTES CL
Gualtherus 1624(1) and 1624(2): CAETVLAS
Tardia: GENTISQ
Muratori; Burmann; Meyer: CAETULAS GENTES CL
Mommsen (1874 letter to Hernandez in Muscolino 2013, 464): Gaetulas gentes
q[ui vicit o che so io] (sic!)
Cordici P and C: GENITO
Tardia: GENITOR
Gualtherus 1624(1) and 1624(2); Cordici P and C; Muratori; Burmann; Meyer:
AENEA DVM
Cordici P and C: PARENS
Tardia: AENIADVVM
Castelli 1769 and 1784: ARMA QVE
Tardia: QUAIE and CESSIT SCVTO C
Cordici P and C; Castelli 1769 and 1784: IN
Tardia: EN
Mommsen (1874 letter to Hernandez in Muscolino 2013, 464): ens[em ...]
Gualtherus 1624(1): ATTRITUS CONSUMATQ
Cordici P and C; Castelli 1769 and 1784: ATTRIT[-] CONSUMMATO
Tardia; Muratori: ATTRITUS CONSUMMAT
Cordici P and C: [---] NI [---] BARBA
Gualtherus 1624(1): POSUI BARBAR
Gualtherus 1624(2): POSUIT BARBAR
Tardia: TNIT
Bücheler (CLE 2.7257): barbar[us ora ferox]
Manganaro: [f]usus barbar[us] eques humi]
Tardia: VTRIQVE and VENE
Dessau 1893 (ILS 937): venera[bile]
Cordici P and C: ATQVE
Gualtherus 1624(1) and 1624(2): PILIVS
Tardia: IBI and ATQV
Mommsen 1875: [f]ilius atqu[e pater]
Gualtherus 1624(1) and 1624(2); Muratori; Burmann; Meyer: PE
Gualtherus 1624(1) and 1624(2): SV
Mommsen (1874 letter to Hernandez in Muscolino 2013, 464): L. Apronio [L. I.
Philotimo curante]

Translation (it)

Lucio Apronio, figlio di Lucio, Cesiano settemviro epulone /
diede (ciò) in dono a Venere Ericina.

Mentre costui, inviato dal padre proconsole di Libia, /
combatte battaglie vittoriose, il nemico mauritano cade ...

- Colui che ha dedicato a te il gladio fortunato e del padre /
- Apronio l'effigie, nato da un condottiero, fu condottiero /
- anch'egli: costui, vincitore in un giusto confronto, /
- grazie alla toga praetexta, deposta e subito rindossata, /
- fanciullo settemviro, questa veste, che il padre aveva richiesto secondo i riti /
- e che Cesare aveva concesso, a te, o santa, la lascia.

Degli dei ... /

reciproche ... /

il figlio di Apronio, illustre più per le gesta che per il nome, /
dal momento che fu lui in persona a dare alla fuga le genti

getule, /

pose, o dea, l'effigie del caro padre, /
legittimi doni per te, alma madre degli Eneadi, /
e le armi che ha impugnato: lo scudo, infranto dai colpi, /
quanta virtù testimonia! La spada si arrossa dal nemico, /
consunta dalle stragi, e la lancia completa il trofeo /
per opera della quale il barbaro feroce cadde, trafitto nel volto.

Una statua di cui nulla, per entrambi, è più venerabile, /

questo ti consacrarono il figlio e il padre: /

l'eguale cura di entrambi dedicò l'effigie di Cesare; /

venne a gara la pietas, che fu massima in ciascuno dei due.

Per cura di Lucio Apronio figlio di Lucio

Translation (en)

Lucius Apronius, son of Lucius, Caesianus of the board of seven for religious feasts /

gave (this) as a gift to Venus Erycina.

While he, sent by his father proconsul of Libya, /

fights victorious battles, the Mauritanian enemy falls ...

He who dedicated to you the lucky sword and the statue of his

father /

Apronius, born of a commander, was a commander /

himself: he, victorious in a fair confrontation, /

because of the toga praetexta, deposed and immediately re-

worn, /

youthful member of the board of seven, this robe, which his

preserved epigram (section b), lines 1-6 of the right column would contain the beginnings of the second epigram (section c), and line 7 would indicate the dedicator (section e). The lost but previously recorded fragment would contain the final part of the second epigram (section c) and the first words of the third (section d1) and fourth epigrams (section d2) in a single column (d). The preserved and the lost fragments would thus be two pieces out of a hypothetical four, namely the second and the fourth from the left, as reconstructed by Mommsen and Bücheler (Mommsen 1875 and CIL 10. 7257), according to whom the inscription, as a whole, would have been inscribed on the basis for three statues: on the left that of L. Apronius C. f., cos. suff. in 8 CE; on the right that of his son L. Apronius Caesianus L. f. VIIvir epulonum and cos. in 39 CE; in the centre that of the emperor Tiberius.

If the integration proposed on the basis of the other fragment now lost but recorded (Gualtherus 1624(1) and 1624(2), Cordici P and C, Tardia, Castelli 1769) is accepted, the whole slab, assuming that the module of the letters was consistent, would have extended at least 40 cm further on the left and 50 cm further on the right, with a total width that could have been at least ca. 120 cm.

The inscription is a dedication to Venus Erycina by L. Apronius – most likely L. Apronius Caesianus, cos. in 39 CE (Groag 1933, A 972 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/000203557#access>] – son of L. Apronius cos. suff. in 8 AD and proconsul in Africa from 18 to 21 CE (Groag 1933, A 971 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/000203557#access>] ; Thomasson 1996, 29 no. 21). If the prevailing hypothesis of Mommsen and Bücheler (Mommsen 1875; CIL 10.7257; CLE 2.1525) is correct, the inscription would consist of four epigrams – with Lucretian resonances such as Aeneadum alma parens (Velaza 2020, 7 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/002031714#access>]) – possibly carmina facilitata, like the verses against Tiberius attributed to Sex. Paconianus and mentioned in Tac. Ann. 6.39 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:6.39>] (Manganaro 1987, 584). Although it is perhaps not so significant with respect to the presence in Sicily of a poetic tradition in Latin, and of an audience that could appreciate it, as Manganaro states (1988, 61). The context of the inscription can be found in the war in proconsular Africa against Tacfarinas (Le Bohec 2020 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/002017573#access>] ; Wolff 2015 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/001477279#access>] ; Vanacker 2015 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/001434329#access>]), for which the proconsul most likely was granted the insignia triumphalia for the second time (Tac. Ann 4.23.1 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:4.23>] ; Eck 1999a, s.v. Apronius II.1, Stuttgart, 1999, vol. I, col. 916 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/000345909#access>]) – the first for the victory against Chatti as legatus of Germanicus (Tac. Ann. 1.56, 72 [<http://data.perseus.org/>

citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:1.56] ; cfr. Vell. 2.116).

The monument itself could be considered as a particular type of trophy (Picard 1957, 247-248). We know that in one of the battles Caesianus, maybe as tribune or even without official position (CIL 10.7257; Rohden 1895 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/000728494#access>] ; Eck 1999b, s.v. Apronius II.2, Stuttgart, 1999, vol. I, col. 916 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/000345909#access>]), fought valiantly at the head of cavalry and auxiliary cohorts and of some legionaries, and drove the enemies back into the desert (Tac. Ann. 3.21 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:3.21>]). The young Apronius would therefore have dedicated his arms (Line 1, section c; Lines 6-9, section d1) and toga (line 4, section c), possibly worn by his own statue (CIL 10.7257), to the goddess Venus of Eryx, and would have built a statue for his father (lines 1-2, section c; line 5, section d1) and one for Tiberius, this one consecrated with his same father (lines 2-3 section d2). Caesianus, called puer in the inscription maybe because of the early and unusual age – perhaps 22 – of his membership in the priestly college of the septemviri epulonum (Várhely 2010 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/000855175#access>] , 68-69), would have been honored by the priesthood by Tiberius, maybe because he was too young for a magistracy, and it is also possible that the toga praetexta dedicated to Venus was the one worn to the first meeting of the college or an additional award (CIL 10 7257; Cagnat 1892, 14-15; Rohden 1895 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/Record/000728494#access>]). It has been hypothesized (Manganaro 1987, 584 followed by Bivona 2000, 154) that the dedication was made by Caesianus on his way back to Rome towards Africa, thus in 21 CE, while the idea that the septemviratus may have been granted to both father and son for this victory (Wilson 1990, 284 n. 244) is not necessary, as Apronius' father probably gained the insignia triumphalia because of the same success.

However, it is also possible that the dedication could be dated to 25 CE, when Tiberius accepted the request of the Segestans to provide, also in the name of the mythical origins of the gens Iulia, a contribution to the restoration of the temple (Tac. Ann. 4.43.4 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:4.43>]) – later completed under Claudius (Suet. Claud. 25.5 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1348.abo015.perseus-lat1:25.5>]) – as the reference in the inscription to the Aeneadum alma parens might suggest. Moreover, the war against Tacfarinas ended only in 24 CE, thanks to the proconsul of 23-24 CE P. Cornelius Dolabella (Thomasson 1996, 30, no. 23), who did not receive the triumphal insignia from Tiberius in order not to obscure the previous deeds of Iunius Blaesus (Tac. Ann. 4.23-26 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:4.23>]), proconsul in 21-23 CE (Thomasson 1996, 30, no. 22; Giovagnoli 2018 [<https://zenon.dainst.org/>]

Record/001593248#access]), who was instead allowed to be acclaimed imperator (Tac. Ann. 3.74.4 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:3.74>]) also because of his kinship with the praefectus praetorio Sejanus (Tac. Ann. 3.72 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:3.72>]). However, the conclusion of the conflict is not itself a conclusive consideration for dating it post 24: honorary statues had been erected in Rome in honour of Camillus, Apronius and Blaesus for their African exploits before Dolabella's decisive intervention (Tac. Ann. 4.23.1 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi1351.phi005.perseus-lat1:4.23>]). This suggests that the war was proclaimed as being over more than once.

The two hypotheses are not mutually exclusive: if the dedicated spoils suggest a time near to Apronius' victory, a later reconstruction or maybe an extension of the monument is also possible. The fact that the execution of this epigraph is rather clumsy, as Mommsen noted (CIL 10 7257: "litterae carminis minutae sunt et male factae"), does not suggest that the monument in its entirety was not of particular value. The apparent epigraphic inexperience may be due, in fact, to a stone mason more skilled in Greek than in Latin. In any case, the inscription is an official dedication in a famous temple and involves Tiberius himself, and it is an important example of senatorial self-representation, more frequent in the provinces than in Rome with the exception of those who obtained ornamenta triumphalia.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175710

EDR 092733

EDH 006236

EDCS 22000842

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic000537>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4384888](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4384888)

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2022-04-07): ISic000537. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6421667>

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